

Notes

Thermodynamic Functions and Stability Constants of Tl(III) Glycollates

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IN continuation of our work on study of some metal complexes with α -hydroxy acids^{1,4}, the present communication deals with the thermodynamic study of Tl(III)-glycollic acid system in solution.

Experimental

Thallic oxide (Schuchardt, Munchen), perchloric acid (Riedel), Sodium perchlorate (Riedel), Glycollic acid (A. R. BDH) and Sodium hydroxide (Merck) have been used in the present investigation.

Solutions were prepared in double distilled, conductivity water and standardised by standard methods. Thallic oxide was dissolved in minimum quantity of dil. HCl and then diluted with water to required volume.

pH measurements were done using 'Systronics' type 322, pH-meter. pH titrations were done in a specially designed cell with an outer jacket, through which water at a fixed temperature from a thermostat was being circulated throughout the experiment. The cell was covered by a plastic lid having appropriate holes to accommodate the electrodes, burette nozzle and the nitrogen bubbling device. The reaction solution was stirred magnetically every time before taking the reading.

Ratio-titrations. Nair and Pande's⁵ monovariation method was used for potentiometric pH titrations to determine the stoichiometry of the complexes formed between Tl(III) and glycollic acid in solution. The ratio titrations indicate the formation of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 complexes, with the liberation of one, two and three protons respectively.

Stability constants. Formation constants at three temperatures, 30°, 40° and 50° have been determined by Calvin-Bjerrum's method⁶. The following mixtures were prepared for titration of glycollic acid in absence and in presence of Tl(III) ions:

- 5 ml 0.02M perchloric acid + 10 ml 0.04M glycollic acid + 4.5 ml 1.0M sodium perchlorate,
- mixture (a) + 5 ml 0.002 M thallium.

The total volume of the mixture in each case was kept 50 ml, thus making the ionic strength 0.1M of sodium perchlorate, and titrated separately against carbon dioxide free standard alkali.

The pK_a values for glycollic acid at 30°, 40° and 50° have been calculated from the pH values corresponding to the calculated half neutralisation point in the titration of the ligand and are found to be 3.82, 3.835 and 3.849 respectively. They are in good agreement with those reported earlier by conductometric method^{7,8}.

Results and Discussion

A perusal of data indicates that the titration curves, for glycollic acid in presence of Tl(III) ions lie lower to that for the acid alone, indicating clearly the liberation of protons due to chelation.

Liberation of one, two and three protons in the formation of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 complexes respectively (in the ratio titrations) suggests that only carboxylic hydrogen protonates during chelation of glycollic acid molecule, while the hydrogen of the α -hydroxyl group remains unaffected. Thus, the following reaction sequence may be suggested for the stepwise formation of the complexes.

where HL = glycollic acid.

In accordance with these reactions the probable structure for the complexes may be given as follows:

where $n = 1, 2$ or 3 .

(In cases of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes, the remaining co-ordination positions may be occupied by water moles). pH titrations indicate that the precipitation starts at ~ 4.3 pH on increasing the amount of alkali added to the system. Hence, it is worth mentioning that the values of $\bar{n}$ have been calculated upto the points to which the solutions were quite clear.

Table 1 records the formation constants at 30°, 40° and 50°. The values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ are directly obtained from the formation curves from the values of $p|L^-|$ at $\bar{n} = 0.5, 1.5$ and 2.5 respectively.

Thermodynamic parameters. The thermodynamic functions, free energy change, ΔF , enthalpy, ΔH and

TABLE 1. FORMATION CONSTANTS

Temp. °C	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃	log β_3
30	4.04	3.87	3.78	11.69
40	4.00	3.81	3.72	11.53
50	3.99	3.80	3.68	11.47

entropy changes, ΔS have been calculated at 30°, utilising Vant Hoff's isotherm for ΔF , graphical solution of Vant Hoff's isobar equation for ΔH and Gibbs Helmholtz equation for ΔS . The first step and the overall functions [ΔF_1 , ΔH_1 , ΔS_1 and ΔF_3 , ΔH_3 and ΔS_3] calculated are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2. THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTION AT 30°

Free energy change K cal/mole		Enthalpy K cal/mole		Entropy cal/degree/mole	
ΔF_1	ΔF_3	ΔH_1	ΔH_3	ΔS_1	ΔS_3
-5.61	-16.24	-1.841	-4.601	+12.43	38.41

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Heterocyclic N-oxide Adducts of Dioxomolybdenum(VI) Salts

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WELL defined stable dioxomolybdenum (VI) complexes are relatively sparse. Though the oxomolybdenum(VI) species mainly occurs as MoO_4^{4-} , MoO_3^{2+} , MoO_3 and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7^{2+}$, they are poorly characterised indeed in their complexes as also in simple compounds owing to the complex nature of condensation and polymerisation they undergo, in a wide variety of experimental conditions. However, in recent years some complexes of dioxomolybdenum(VI) ion having compositions $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{L}_2$ (L = unidentate ligand, viz., Ph_3PO , PhCOCH_3 , PhCHO , THF , CH_3CN , DMSO , HMPA)¹⁻³ and $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{L}'$ (L' = bidentate ligand, viz., acetylacetone, benzil, etc.)² have been isolated and characterized.

Herein is reported some heterocyclic N-oxide complexes of dioxomolybdenum (VI) chloride and nitrate, the composition, some physical properties and analytical data of which are presented in Table 1.

These complexes are synthesized using $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as a starting material prepared by standard method⁴. The above mentioned easily sublimable compound in solution in dry acetone afforded the chloro complexes by boiling with the acetone solutions of the N-oxides mixed in 1:2 mole ratio with respect to metal and ligand. For isolating the nitrate complex, $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in dry acetonitrile was allowed to undergo substitution and subsequently precipitation reaction with AgNO_3 also taken in dry acetonitrile and precipitated AgCl was filtered off and the filtrate, containing dioxomolybdenum (VI) nitrate was allowed to react with double its mole proportion of 4-nitropyridine N-oxide. Curiously enough, under the same experimental condition pyridine and quinoline N-oxides do not afford any pure isolable product. All of these compounds are insoluble in benzene, light petroleum, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform but very moderately soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetone, and acetonitrile, excepting the nitrate complex which is insoluble in all organic solvents. The chloro com-

Table I

Compound	Colour	M.P. (°C)	Decomposition* temp. (°C)	Percent**				
				C	H	N	Cl	Mo
$\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2(\text{PyNO})$	White	178(d)	150	31.1 (30.9)	2.51 (2.57)	7.26 (7.20)	18.1 (18.2)	24.9 (14.7)
$\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2(4\text{-NO}_2\text{PyNO})_2$	White	200(d)	200	24.9 (25.1)	1.69 (1.67)	11.6 (11.7)	14.9 (14.8)	19.6 (20.0)
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2(4\text{-NO}_2\text{PyNO})_2$	Yellow	190(d)	150	22.8 (22.6)	1.55 (1.50)	15.6 (15.8)	—	18.3 (18.0)
$\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_3(\text{QNO})_2$	Yellow	201(d)	194	44.5 (44.2)	2.84 (2.86)	5.76 (5.73)	14.4 (14.5)	19.5 (19.6)

*obtained from TGA curves; **calculated percentages are given in parentheses.